

Policy-making in the Big Data Era: Opportunities and Challenges

15-17 June 2015
University of Cambridge

Information Pack

About Data for Policy 2015

Current decision-making processes are far from being optimal to represent the best interests of the public and stakeholders, as contemporary policy domains are very complex, high dimensional and include a large dose of uncertainty. The massive amounts of data captured in our physical world through sensors and electronic devices provide a huge potential to advance these processes. With the availability of new technologies, new formulations are needed on fundamental questions such as how to conduct a census, how to produce labour statistics, or how to incorporate data mined from social media and administrative operations. Efficient procedures to draw links between large-scale data-processing technologies and existing expert knowledge in major policy domains would potentially offer chances to make policy development processes more citizen-focused, taking into account public needs and preferences supported with actual experiences of public services. This however comes with serious privacy and security concerns as intersecting various data sources could reveal unprecedented private information.

The conference committee invited contributions covering the following topics:

- Information and evidence in digital age
- Policy-making mechanisms and modelling approaches
- Existing methodologies, case studies, best practices for use of Big Data in policy
- Data collection, storage, processing and access procedures
- Cumulative learning in digital environments, potentials in policy context, challenges and limitations
- Interaction of domain expertise with digital processing technologies; dealing with imperfect/uncertain data; psychology/behaviour of decision
- Security and privacy issues; ethics and law

Dates: 15-17 June 2015

Venue: William Gates Building, 15 JJ Thomson Avenue, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB3 0FD

Conference Organisers

Convenors:

- Zeynep **Engin**, Founder, dataforpolicy.uk; Director, London Centre for Social Studies; Fellow, University of Cambridge
- Jon **Crowcroft**, Marconi Professor of Communications Systems, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

Conference Committee:

- Anne **Alexander**, Digital Humanities Network, Centre for Research in the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities (CRASSH), University of Cambridge
- Jean **Bacon**, Professor Emerita of Distributed Systems, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge
- Kenneth **Benoit**, Professor of Political Science Research Methodology and Head of the Department of Methodology, London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE)
- Anil **Bharath**, Research Board Member, Data Science Institute, Imperial College London
- Simon **Burall**, Director, Involve; Head of Dialogue, ScienceWise Expert Resource Centre
- Deeph **Chana**, Senior Research Fellow, Institute for Security Science & Technology, Imperial College London
- Jon **Crowcroft**, Marconi Professor of Communications Systems, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge
- Suleyman Sirri **Demirsoy**, Director, London Innovation Society
- Rob **Doubleday**, Executive Director, Centre for Science and Policy, University of Cambridge
- Clare **Dyer-Smith**, Cambridge Big Data Strategic Research Initiative
- Zeynep **Engin**, Founder, dataforpolicy.uk; Director, London Centre for Social Studies; Fellow, University of Cambridge
- Moira **Faul**, Research Associate, Centre for Science and Policy, University of Cambridge
- Andrew **Gamble**, Professor of Politics, Department of Politics and International Studies (POLIS), University of Cambridge
- Bilal **Gokpinar**, Assistant Professor / Management Science and Innovation, University College London
- David J **Hand**, Emeritus Professor of Mathematics, Imperial College; Chair, UK's Administrative Data Research Network
- Neil **Lindsay**, Professor, Senior Advisor to the Counter-Terrorism Science and Technology Centre, DSTL
- Eric T **Meyer**, Associate Professor and Director of Graduate Studies, Oxford Internet Institute, University of Oxford
- John **Naughton**, Emeritus Professor of the Public Understanding of Technology, Wolfson College, University of Cambridge

- Jeff **Patmore**, Innovator, Researcher, and Mentor in Information and Communications Technology (ICT); Industry Fellow, Engineering Design Centre, University of Cambridge
- David **Reiner**, University Senior Lecturer in Technology Policy, Judge Business School, University of Cambridge
- Jasdeep **Sandhu**, Policy Fellow, Centre for Science and Policy, University of Cambridge
- Hetan **Shah**, Executive Director, Royal Statistical Society (RSS)
- Emre **Simsekler**, Researcher, University College London; London Innovation Society
- Mesut **Tastan**, Fellow, London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE); London Innovation Society
- Ian **Walden**, Professor of Information and Communications Law, Queen Mary, University of London; Solicitor of the Senior Courts of England and Wales
- Antony **Walker**, Deputy CEO, techUK; Policy Fellow, Centre for Science and Policy, University of Cambridge
- Glenn **Watson**, Director-General, Office for National Statistics (ONS)
- Stian **Westlake**, Executive Director, Policy & Research, Nesta
- James **Wilsdon**, Professor of Science and Democracy at SPRU (Science & Technology Policy Research) , Sussex University
- Eiko **Yoneki**, EPSRC Research Fellow, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

Partner institutions:

- London Centre for Social Studies (LCSS)
- Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge
- Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge
- Data Science Institute (DSI), Imperial College London
- Department of Methodology, London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE)
- The Royal Statistical Society (RSS)
- Sciencewise Programme funded by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills (BIS)
- Office for National Statistics (ONS)
- London Innovation Society (LIS)
- Cambridge Big Data, University of Cambridge
- Digital Humanities Network, University of Cambridge

Programme Overview

Monday, 15 June 2015:

08:45 – 09:15 Arrivals and registration
09:15 – 09:35 Welcome and Introductions
09:35 – 10:30 Keynote 1
10:30 – 11:00 Break
11:00 – 12:20 Parallel Session 1
12:20 – 13:30 Lunch Break
13:30 – 14:25 Keynote 2
14:25 – 15:45 Policy Session 1
15:45 – 16:15 Break
16:15 – 17:35 Parallel Session 2

Tuesday, 16 June 2015:

08:45 – 09:15 Arrivals and registration
09:15 – 10:10 Keynote 3
10:10 – 10:30 LIS Poster Competition – 2min presentations
10:30 – 11:00 Break
11:00 – 12:20 Parallel Session 3
12:20 – 13:40 Lunch Break & LIS Poster Session
13:40 – 14:35 Keynote 4
14:35 – 15:55 Policy Session 2
15:55 – 16:25 Break
16:25 – 17:45 Parallel Session 4

19: 30 Conference Dinner at Cambridge City Hotel

Wednesday, 17 June 2015:

08:45 – 09:15 Arrivals and registration
09:15 – 10:10 Keynote 5
10:10 – 10:40 Break
10:40 – 12:00 Parallel Session 5
12:00 – 13:30 Lunch Break
13:30 – 14:50 Parallel Session 6
14:50 – 15:20 Break
15:20 – 16:40 Closing Session
16:40 End

Monday, 15 June 2015

08:45 – 09:15 Arrivals and registration

09:15 – 09:35 Welcome and Introductions – Zeynep **Engin**, Jon **Crowcroft** (Room: LT1)

09:35 – 10:30 Keynote 1 (Room: LT1)

Kenneth **Benoit**, Professor of Political Science Research Methodology and Head of the Department of Methodology, London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE) - *“Ten challenges of Big Data for Social Science”*

Chair: David **Howarth**, Former LibDem MP for Cambridge, Reader in Law and Director of the MPhil in Public Policy, University of Cambridge

10:30 – 11:00 Break

11:00 – 12:20 Parallel Session 1

Session 1a: “Political Communication” – **Chair:** Ian **Walden**, Professor of Information and Communications Law, Queen Mary, University of London; Solicitor of the Senior Courts of England and Wales – (Room: LT1)

Alison **Powell**, LSE; Nick **Anstead**, LSE; Les **Carr** University of Southampton; Susan **Halford**, University of Southampton; Dhiraj **Murthy**, Goldsmiths College; and Mark **Weal**, University of Southampton – *“Do Bots of a Feather Flock Together? Analysing the role of Twitter bot behaviour in political discussion”*

Peter **Burnap** and Matthew **Williams**, Cardiff University, UK – *“Computational Cyber and Human Security Analytics using Big Data”*

Thomas Hunter **Smith**, Office for National Statistics, UK – *“Big Data, Twitter and the Scottish Referendum”*

Jonathan **Bright**, Helen **Margetts**, Scott **Hale** and Taha **Yasseri**, Oxford Internet Institute, University of Oxford – *“Social reflection of new policies in the big data era”*

Rapporteur: Andree **Riberio**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

Session 1b: “The Cabinet Office, ethics and data science” organised jointly by the **UK Cabinet Office** and **Sciencewise** - **Chair:** Peter **Smith**, Professor of Social Statistics, Director of the ESRC Administrative Data Research Centre for England, University of Southampton – (Room: LT2)

Paul **Maltby**, Director of Open Data and Government Innovation at the Cabinet Office

Cat **Drew**, Senior Policy Adviser, Data Science at the Cabinet Office

Simon **Burall**, Head of Dialogue at Sciencewise Expert Resource Centre

Rapporteur: Leanne **Melbourne**, Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge

Session 1c (FW26): “*Communications*” organised by the **London Innovation Society (LIS)**
– **Chair:** Anil **Bharath**, Imperial College London – (Room: FW26)

Mustafa **Ergen**, Turk Telekom Argela – “*Big Data in Telecommunications*”

Syed Ali Raza **Zaidi**, University of Leeds; Mounir **Ghogho**, University of Leeds;
Muhammad Ali **Imran**, University of Surrey; and Selcuk **Bassoy**, University of Surrey
– “*Big Data Empowered Self Organization For Split Plane 5G Cellular Networks*”

Lun **Liu** and Elisabete **Silva**, University of Cambridge – “*Planning for sustainable urban transport: An activity-based model with large-scale travel diary, POI and review sites data*”

Rapporteur: Suleyman **Demirsoy**, London Innovation Society (LIS)

12:20 – 13:30 Lunch Break

13:30 – 14:25 Keynote 2 – (Room: LT1)

Ross **Anderson**, Professor of Security Engineering, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge - “*Ethics in the Age of Big Data*”

Chair: Sir David **Wallace**, Former Master of Churchill College, University of Cambridge

14:25 – 15:45 Policy Session 1 – (Room: LT1)

“*Big Data for Government*” – **Chair:** Derek **Wyatt**, Former Labour MP for Sittingbourne and Sheppey, Co-chairman of All Party Communications Group

Jane **Naylor**, Senior Principal Methodologist, Office for National Statistics - “*Big Data - A Big Issue for Official Statistics*”

Hetan **Shah**, Executive Director, Royal Statistical Society (RSS) - “*A manifesto for data informed policy*”

Jo **Dally**, Deputy Director for Data Analysis, Horizon Scanning and Project Development, Government Office for Science (GO-Science) - “*Big data: big opportunity; big brother; or big trouble?*”

Antony **Walker**, Deputy CEO, techUK – *Title TBC*

Rapporteur: Leanne **Melbourne**, Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge

15:45 – 16:15 Break

16:15 – 17:35 Parallel Session 2

Session 2a: *"From Point of Care to Policy: Public Health in the Era of Big Data"* - **Chair:** Paul **Matthews**, Professor of Clinical Neuroscience at Imperial College London – (Room: LT1)

Mark **Bale**, Deputy Head of Health Science and Bioethics Division at the Department of Health – *"Genomics England and delivering the Prime Minister's 100,000 genomes initiative"*

Alison **Hall**, Public Health Genomics Foundation – *"Reconciling the interests of individuals and populations in policy development in genomics"*

May **Yong**, Paul **Matthews** and Yike **Guo**, Imperial College London – *"OPTIMISE (Optimisation of Prognosis and Treatment In Multiple Sclerosis) – A platform for maximizing the use of large scale longitudinal multiple sclerosis patient data"*

Rapporteur: Jessica **Banslaben**, Fordham University

Session 2b: *"Innovation activities for economic development"* – **Chair:** Elisabete A **Silva** - Department of Land Economy, University of Cambridge – (Room: LT2)

Alexander **Kleibrink**, Joint Research Centre, European Commission, Spain – *"Data-driven innovation policies in Europe: Mapping methods and sources"*

Viktoria **Spaiser**, Ranganathan **Shyam**, Ranjula Bali **Swain** and David J.T. **Sumpter**, Uppsala University, Sweden – *"Building an index for Sustainable Development Goals Using a Dynamical Systems Data-Science Approach"*

Tom **Crick**, Cardiff Metropolitan University; Juan **Mateos-Garcia**, Nesta; Hasan **Bakhshi**, Nesta; Stian **Westlake**, Nesta – *"Innovation Policy-Making in the Big Data Era"*

Dave **Excell**, Featurespace; Georgiy **Bobashev**, RTI; Heather **Wardle**, NatCen; Daniel **Gonzalez-Ordonez**, Featurespace; Tom **Whitehead**, Featurespace; Robert **Morris**, RTI; Paul **Ruddle**, RTI; Amelia **Caron**, Featurespace - *"Shaping Responsible Gambling Policy: a case study of harm minimisation research"*

Rapporteur: Dominik **Jung**, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow

Session 2c: *"Big Data for Policy - critics & limits"* – **Chair:** Alan **Blackwell**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge – (Room: FW26)

Emma **Uprichard**, University of Warwick – *"Big Data is Good for Big Bad Policy: Why big data cannot help complex social policy and planning"*

Francesco **Mureddu** and David **Osimo**, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya and Open Evidence, Spain – *"Data-driven policy making between myths and reality"*

Ralph **Schroeder**, Josh **Cowls** and Eric T **Meyer**, Oxford Internet Institute, University

of Oxford – *“Mining Data about the Public as a Tool for Policy”*

John **Sheridan**, Head of Legislation Services, The National Archives – *“Using data to understand how the statute book works”*

Rapporteur: Charlotte **Sausman**, Public Policy SRI, University of Cambridge

Tuesday, 16 June 2015

08:45 – 09:15 Arrivals and registration

09:15 – 10:10 Keynote 3 – (Room: LT1)

David J **Hand**, Emeritus Professor of Mathematics, Imperial College; Chair, UK's Administrative Data Research Network - "*Big data: promise and pitfalls*"

Chair: Heather **Savory**, Director General for Data Capability, Office for National Statistics

10:10 – 10:30 LIS Poster Competition – 2min presentations – (Room: LT1)

10:30 – 11:00 Break

11:00 – 12:20 Parallel Session 3

Session 3a: "*Information retrieval and data processing*" – **Chair:** Jon **Crowcroft**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge – (Room: LT1)

Mirco **Musolesi**, University College London – "*Real-time Policy-making: Merging New and Old Big Data*"

Eugen **Molnar**, Comenius University and Rastislav **Molnar**, Imperial College London - "*Intelligent Web Technology for the Policy-making Process and Policy Evaluation*"

Omar **Guerrero** and Eduardo **Lopez**, University of Oxford – "*Microdata, Networks, and Simulation for Unemployment Policy*"

Konstantinos **Psannis**, University of Macedonia, Greece – "*Toward Convergence of Information Theory for Efficient Data Collection, Storage and Access*"

Rapporteur: Jennifer **Crees**, National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO)

Session 3b: "*Big data for evidence-informed policy: International inventory and European Commission case studies*" - **Chair:** Eric **Meyer**, Oxford Internet Institute (OII) – (Room: LT2)

Prabhat **Agarwal**, Head of Sector 'Evidence-based policy-making', DG CONNECT, European Commission

Martijn **Poel**, Technopolis Group

Ralph **Schroeder**, Professor, Oxford Internet Institute, University of Oxford

Rapporteur: Ella **McPherson**, Department of Sociology, University of Cambridge

Session 3c: “Healthcare applications” organised by the **London Innovation Society (LIS)**
– **Chair:** Jeffrey Ng, Stratified Medical – (Room: FW26)

Mike **Standing**, Deloitte – *“Transforming healthcare data through analytics”*

Oriol **Sola-Morales** and Eduard **Gil**, Sagessa, Spain – *“Data mining to leverage change in clinical practice”*

Joanna **Chataway**, RAND Europe – *“Assessing the Real-World Data Policy Landscape for Health and Healthcare in Europe”*

Chris **Rands**, Public Health Genomics Foundation – *“Clinical genomic data sharing for healthcare: practical and policy challenges”*

Rapporteur: Emre **Simsekler**, London Innovation Society (LIS)

12:20 – 13:40 Lunch Break (LIS Poster Session)

13:40 – 14:35 Keynote 4 – (Room: LT1)

James **Wilsdon**, Professor of Science and Democracy at SPRU (Science & Technology Policy Research), Sussex University – *“The Metric Tide: big data and the future of research assessment”*

Chair: Ralph **Schroeder**, Oxford Internet Institute (OII)

14:35 – 15:55 Policy Session 2 – (Room: LT1)

“Data science - the opportunities and challenges for government” organised by the **UK Cabinet Office** - **Chair:** Bill **Oates**, Chief Data Scientist, Office for National Statistics

Sue **Bateman**, Head of Data Science, Cabinet Office – *“Data science in government - the benefits and challenges of implementing new analytical techniques and technologies in government”*

Shahzia **Holtom**, Data Scientist, Government Digital Service – *“Using the National Energy Efficiency Data Framework (NEED) to better target energy efficiency measures”*

Dan **Heron**, Data Scientist, Government Digital Service – *“Exploring how complaints from departmental and non-departmental sources can predict surges in service demand”*

Nigel **Swier**, Principal Methodologist, Big Data Project, Office for National Statistics – *“Using web scraped data to supplement the Consumer and Retail Price Indexes”*

Rapporteur: Tom **Rodger**, Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge

15:55 – 16:25 Break

16:25 – 17:45 Parallel Session 4

Session 4a: *"Applications, challenges and policy implications of Big Data in business world"* organised by the **London Innovation Society (LIS)**, **Chair:** Mesut **Tastan**, London School of Economics – (Room: LT1)

Paul **Jones**, SAS - *"The advent of Big Data technologies in Finance"*

David **Bholat**, Bank of England – *"Big data and central banks"*

Carla **Bonina**, Surrey Business School – *"The value of big data and its consequences: ethics, controversies and policy"*

Harald **Stieber**, Ralph **Dum** and Prabhat **Agarwal**, European Commission, Belgium – *"Which data for monitoring financial stability? Policy issues related to collecting, processing, and aggregating increasingly granular financial sector data"*

Rapporteur: Jennifer **Crees**, National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO)

Session 4b: *"Testing Big Data – do large data sets help reduce uncertainty?"* organised by **Sense about Science** – **Chair:** Ella **McPherson**, ESRC Future Research Leader Fellow, Department of Sociology, University of Cambridge – (Room: LT2)

David J. **Hand**, Imperial College London – *"Big Data, uncertainty and probability in public policy"*

Prateek **Buch**, Sense about Science – *"Testing Big Data – does complex data help reduce uncertainty?"*

Phil **Bradburn**, National Audit Office – *Title TBC*

Rapporteur: Tom **Rodger**, Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge

Session 4c: *"Applications"* – **Chair:** John **Sheridan**, Head of Legislation Services, The National Archives – (Room: FW26)

Juan **Mateos-Garcia** and Hasan **Bakhshi**, Nesta, UK – *"Using big data to map an innovative industry: the case of the UK video games industry"*

Boris **Adryan**, University of Cambridge – *"What the Internet of Things should learn from the biosciences"*

Giuditta **De Prato**, EC JRC IPTS, Spain; Jean Paul **Simon**, JPS Multimedia, France; Jesus Vega **Villa**, EC JRC IPTS, Spain – *"Evidence based support to policy making in the Big Data Era: Understanding the context and learning from experiences in transitioning from 'fat data' to 'big data' "*

Rapporteur: Carlos **Molina-Jimenez**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

19: 30 Conference Dinner at Cambridge City Hotel

Wednesday, 17 June 2015

08:45 – 09:15 Arrivals and registration

09:15 – 10:10 Keynote 5 – (Room: LT1)

Natasa **Milic-Frayling**, Microsoft Research Cambridge (MSRC) – *“Speaking up for us, the citizens: Whose policy, whose data, whose benefits?”*

Chair: Jon **Crowcroft**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

10:10 – 10:40 Break

10:40 – 12:00 Parallel Session 5

Session 5a: *Information and evidence for policy-making* – **Chair:** Will **Moy**, Full Fact – (Room: LT1)

Richard **Harries**, Deputy Director, Reform - *“Governing by numbers”*

Gavin **Freeguard**, Senior Researcher working on Whitehall Monitor, Institute for Government – *“Communicating with the public”*

Finbarr **Livesey**, University of Cambridge, UK – *“How do UK voters want to engage with Parliament?”*

John **Taysom**, RVC, UK – *“See what a state the maintenance of “state” has got the State in!”*

Rapporteur: Carlos **Molina-Jimenez**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

Session 5b: *“Big Data challenges for journalism and policy-making”* organised by **Digital Humanities Network**, University of Cambridge – **Chair:** Anne **Alexander**, University of Cambridge – (Room: LT2)

Roxane **Farmanfarmaian**, University of Cambridge-al-Jazeera Media Project, POLIS, University of Cambridge – *“Policy considerations for Responsibility-in-Use: Mediating Big Data in the Public Sphere”*

Ella **McPherson** and Anne **Alexander**, University of Cambridge – *“The Representational and Ethical Limitations of Using Social Media Data Real-Time for Policy-Making”*

Liliana **Bounegru**, Jonathan **Gray** and Tommaso **Venturini** – *“Narrating Networks of Power: Narrative Structures of Network Analysis for Journalism”*

Jonathan **Gray**, Open Knowledge Foundation – *“Are we measuring the right things? From disclosure and data portals to participatory data infrastructures”*

Rapporteur: Jessica **Banslaben**, Fordham University

Session 5c: “*Urban planning, disaster recovery, and environment*” – **Chair:** Eiko Yoneki, University of Cambridge – (Room: FW26)

Chaowei **Xiao** and Elisabete **Silva**, University of Cambridge, UK – “*From Big Data Sets to Collective Human Behavior Patterns and Urban Spatial Structure - Analyzing and Simulating Spatial-Temporal Dynamics in Shanghai*”

Rohan **Samarajiva** and Sriganesh **Lokanathan**, LIRNEasia, Sri Lanka – “*Using mobile-network big data for urban & transportation planning in Colombo, Sri Lanka*”

Timothy **Wilson**, United Nations Economic Commission in Africa (UNECA), Rwanda – “*Big data and the monitoring of post-disaster economies*”

Hank **Koerten** and Peter van den **Besselaar**, VU University, Netherlands – “*Natural History Museums in Europe as hybridized research infrastructures: faded glory or a digital phoenix rising from its ashes?*”

Rapporteur: Andree **Riberio**, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

12:00 – 13:30 Lunch Break

13:30 – 14:50 Parallel Session 6

Session 6a: “*Processing government data*” – **Chair:** Pieter van **Houten**, Department of Politics and International Studies (POLIS), University of Cambridge – (Room: LT1)

Alessandro **Piscopo**, University of Amsterdam, Centrum Wiskunde, Informatica; Ronald **Siebes**, VU University Amsterdam; and Lynda **Hardman**, Centrum Wiskunde, Informatica, Netherlands – “*Predicting sense of community and participation by applying machine learning to open government data*”

Vania **Sena**, University of Essex – “*Dealing with Big Data in the Local Government*”

Hannah **Durrant** and Julie **Barnett**, University of Bath, UK – “*Using ‘big data’ to inform local policy decisions*”

Andrew **Goodman**, The Home Office – “*Using data to protect the public*”

Rapporteur: Maria **Pikoula**, National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO)

Session 6b: Special Workshops – (Room: LT2)

“*Exploring government administrative data to hold governments accountable in the Big Data Era*” organized by Mihály **Fazekas**, University of Cambridge
(Please note that Participants are encouraged to bring own laptops to jointly explore government contracting data during the workshop)

“Democracy and data: how data-driven policy making can avoid technocracy”, Anthony **Zacharzewski**, Demsoc; Prabhat **Agarwal**, European Commission; Adam **Watson-Brown**, European Commission

Session 6c: “Privacy, Ethics and Law” – Chair: Jat Singh, Computer Laboratory and Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge – (Room: FW26)

David **Garcia**, Emre **Sarigol** and Frank **Schweitzer**, ETH Zurich, Switzerland –
“*Online Social Network Privacy as a Collective Phenomenon*”

Jeffrey **Skopek**, Faculty of Law, University of Cambridge – “*Bodies of Data and the Person in Personalized Medicine*”

Justin **Longo**, Arizona State University; David M. **Hondula**, Arizona State University; Evan R. **Kuras**, Boston University; Erik W. **Johnston**, Arizona State University –
“*Challenges in Revealing the Bright Shadows of the Digitally Invisible*”

Jonathan **Gray**, Richard **Rogers** and Liliana **Bounegru**, Digital Methods Initiative, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands – “*Digital Methods for Public Policy Research: Mapping Open Data as an Issue Online*”

Rapporteur: Dominik **Jung**, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow

14:50 – 15:20 Break (Tea & Coffee)

15:20 – 16:40 Closing Session – (Room: LT1)

“*Reflections from the conference and future projections*” – **Moderator:** Zeynep **Engin**, Founder, dataforpolicy.uk; Director, London Centre for Social Studies; Fellow, University of Cambridge

Eric T **Meyer**, Associate Professor and Director of Graduate Studies, Oxford Internet Institute, University of Oxford

Anne **Alexander**, Digital Humanities Network, Centre for Research in the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities (CRASSH), University of Cambridge

Jon **Crowcroft**, Marconi Professor of Communications Systems, Computer Laboratory, University of Cambridge

16:40 Final remarks and closing

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I agree to dataforpolicy.uk processing personal data contained within the registration process, or other data which may be obtained from me or other people whilst I am applying for the conference. I agree to the processing of such data for any purpose connected with my attendance at the conference, or my health and safety whilst on event premises.

The organisers reserve the right to change conference programme and venue details, and to cancel the conference in case of any unpredictable event.

List of Participants

Boris	Adryan	University of Cambridge
Prabhat	Agarwal	European Commission
Anne	Alexander	Digital Humanities Network, University of Cambridge
William	Allen	University of Oxford
Efe Kerem	Aydin	Data for Policy
Zehra	Aydin	Data for Policy
Hasan	Bakhshi	Nesta
Mark	Bale	Department of Health
Jessica	Bansleben	Fordham University
Julie	Barnett	University of Bath
Sue	Bateman	Cabinet Office
Sarah	Beadle	King's College London
Kenneth	Benoit	London School of Economics and Political Science
Anil	Bharath	Imperial College London
Alan	Blackwell	University of Cambridge
Carla	Bonina	Surrey Business School
Liliana	Bounegru	University of Amsterdam
Phil	Bradburn	National Audit Office
Preteek	Buch	Sense about Science
Simon	Burall	Sciencewise
Peter	Burnap	Cardiff University
Siobhan	Carey	Department for Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS)
Leslie	Carr	University of Southampton
Carl	Chalmers	Liverpool John Moores
Deeph	Chana	Imperial College London
Vikas	Chandra	London School of Economics
Joanna	Chataway	RAND Europe
Natalie	Clewley	Brunel University
Josh	Cowls	Oxford Internet Institute
Ingemar J	Cox	University College London
Jennifer	Crees	National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO)
Jon	Crowcroft	University of Cambridge
Nathan	Cunningham	UK Data Archive, University of Essex
Camilla	d'Angelo	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Valentin	Dalibard	University of Cambridge
Jo	Dally	GO-Science
Paul	Davies	Cisco
Giuditta	De Prato	JRC-IPTS
Antonin	Delpeuch	École Normale Supérieure
Suleyman	Demirsoy	London Innovation Society (LIS)
Rob	Doubleday	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Cat	Drew	Cabinet Office

Hannah	Durrant	University of Bath
Clare	Dyer-Smith	Cambridge Big Data Initiative
Humphrey	Emesowum	University of Portsmouth
Zeynep	Engin	Data for Policy
Mustafa	Ergen	Argela
David	Excell	Featurespace
Roxane	Farmanfarmaian	University of Cambridge
Moira	Faul	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Mihaly	Fazekas	University of Cambridge
Gavin	Freeguard	Institute for Government
David	Garcia	ETH Zurich
Bilal	Gokpinar	University College London (UCL)
Bilal	Gokpinar	University College London
Andrew	Goodman	The Home Office
Jonathan	Gray	Open Knowledge
Omar	Guerrero	University of Oxford, INET & SBS
Alison	Hall	PhG Foundation
David J	Hand	Imperial College London
Shahid	Hanif	Association of the British Pharmaceutical Industry
Richard	Harries	Reform
Daniel	Heron	Government Digital Service, Cabinet Office
Shahzia	Holtom	Government Digital Service, Cabinet Office
Pieter van	Houten	University of Cambridge
David	Howarth	University of Cambridge
Paul	Jones	SAS
Dominik	Jung	University of Strathclyde, Glasgow
Linda	Kahl	The BioBricks Foundation
Seref	Kavak	London Centre for Social Studies (LCSS)
Alexander	Kleibrink	European Commission, Joint Research Centre
Filip	Klimenka	Oxford-Man Institute
Berk	Koc	Data for Policy
Henk	Koerten	VU University
Aleksandra	Laska	Improbable Worlds Ltd.
Shona Shane	Lee	University of Edinburgh
Scott	Limbrick	University of Cambridge
Neil	Lindsay	Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (DSTL)
Lun	Liu	University of Cambridge
Finbarr	Livesey	University of Cambridge
Justin	Longo	Arizona State University
Eduardo	Lopez	University of Oxford
Panos	Louvieris	Brunel University
Iva	Lukac	Liverpool John Moores
Mechmet	Machmout	London Centre for Social Studies (LCSS)
Elaine	Mackey	University of Manchester
Paul	Maltby	Cabinet Office
Helen	Margetts	Oxford Internet Institute

Juan	Mateos-Garcia	Nesta
Paul	Matthews	Imperial College London
Sam	McGregor	Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)
Ella	McPherson	University of Cambridge
Leanne	Melbourne	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Paul	Meller	Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)
Eric	Meyer	Oxford Internet Institute
Carlos	Molina-Jimenez	University of Cambridge
Rastislav	Molnar	Imperial College London
Will	Moy	Full Fact
Francesco	Mureddu	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
Mirco	Musolesi	University College London
John	Naughton	University of Cambridge
Jane	Naylor	Office for National Statistics
Jeffrey	Ng	Stratified Medical
Karthik	Nilakant	University of Cambridge
Bill	Oates	Office for National Statistics
Omer Faruk	Ogutcen	Data for Policy
Jackie	Ouchikh	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Louise	Pakseresht	The Royal Society
CSaP	Pass	
CSaP	Pass	
Jeff	Patmore	University of Cambridge
		National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO)
Maria	Pikoula	
Alessandro	Piscopo	Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica
Martijn	Poel	Technopolis Group
Alison	Powell	London School of Economics and Political Science
Konstantinos	Psanis	University of Macedonia
Malavika	Raghavan	
Charles	Rahal	University of Birmingham
Chris	Rands	PhG Foundation
Mark	Reader	University of Cambridge
David	Reiner	University of Cambridge
Ali	Rezaei Yazdi	Aston University
Yan	Rianto	Ministry of Communication & IT - Indonesia
Andre	Ribeiro	University of Cambridge
Tom	Rodger	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Helen	Rowbottom	University of Cambridge
Rohan	Samarajiva	LIRNEasia
Jasdeep	Sandhu	Department for International Development (DfID)
Iman	Sanjaya	Ministry of Communication & IT - Indonesia
Charlotte	Sausman	University of Cambridge
Heather	Savory	Office for National Statistics
Ralph	Schroeder	Oxford Internet Institute
Vania	Sena	University of Essex

Chanuki	Seresinhe	University of Warwick
Hetan	Shah	Royal Statistical Society (RSS)
John	Sheridan	The National Archives
Bushra	Siddiqi	Imperial College London
Maria	Sigala	Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)
Elisabete	Silva	University of Cambridge
Emre	Simsekler	London Innovation Society (LIS)
Jat	Singh	University of Cambridge
Jeffrey	Skopek	University of Cambridge
Sam	Smith	medConfidential
Thomas		
Hunter	Smith	Office for National Statistics
Adam	Smith	Research Fortnight
Peter	Smith	ADRC England
Viktoria	Spaiser	Uppsala University, Department of Mathematics
Mike	Standing	Deloitte
Harald	Stieber	European Commission
	Suherman-	
Josephine	Bailey	Sciencewise
Mrs.	Sumini	Ministry of Communication & IT - Indonesia
Nigel	Swier	Office for National Statistics
Mesut	Tastan	London School of Economics and Political Science
		Department for Communities and Local
Ricky	Taylor	Government
Sherife	Tekdal	London Centre for Social Studies (LCSS)
John	Tysom	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)
Ufuk	Ucar	London Centre for Social Studies (LCSS)
Emma	Uprichard	University of Warwick
Kubra	Uygur	Data for Policy
Rosa	Vercoe	London Centre for Social Studies (LCSS)
Diana	Vlad-Calcic	European Commission
Ian	Walden	Queen Mary University of London
Antony	Walker	techUK
David	Wallace	University of Cambridge
Matthew	Williams	Cardiff University
James	Wilsdon	University of Sussex
Timothy	Wilson	UN Economic Commission for Africa
Derek	Wyatt	Former Labour MP
Chaowei	Xiao	University of Cambridge
Alev	Yaman	English Pen
Aytac	Yildiz	University of Yildirim Beyazit, Turkey
Eiko	Yoneki	University of Cambridge
Anthony	Zacharzewski	The Democratic Society
Syed Ali Raza	Zaidi	University of Leeds

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